

Virtual Education Summit-

Higher education for democracy in a shifting global landscape

3rd Unite!-Ed Future Conference 2026

Abstracts

Keynote speech

Human-centric education in the age of AI,
Arnold Pears

The adoption of Generative AI, along with other technological advances, has changed the way our students approach their studies and work. In this presentation, we explore the capabilities of these tools and their potential impact on the human-centric focus of education. Given the current threat that generative AI poses to learning autonomy and the temptation to reduce cognitive processing by delegating creative tasks to AI tools, what should we do to retain a human-centric educational model? I argue that learning and education are essentially social activities, and that generative AI is neither a social nor a cognitive agent. This implies that deep learning experiences will still be dominated by human-focused interaction.

Session 1

Moderator: Ernest Ampadu

Experiences in Collaborative Research-based Learning on Engineering for Industry

J. Minguella Canela, E. Çiçek, H. Savolainen, G. Cardeal

The Seed Fund project “Collaborative Learning Environments for Research-based Teaching on Industry 4.0” (CLERT-I4.0) had as core focus to set in action Research-based Collaborative Teaching and Learning on Engineering for Industry, focusing on research topics related to Industry 4.0 and with potential to easily spread to others (Sustainability, Energy, Entrepreneurship).

The way to do so was to convey joint inter-university research assignments, combining the expertise of each research group and teaching centre, and incorporating specific short mobility stays (physical or virtual) fitting well the requirements of each study plan and institution. The design of the research topics was enhanced by first proposing priorities by each research group participating in the initiative and then identifying the interaction points between the different objectives and fields to draft attractive collaborations. The set in action of the projects included interaction spaces between the students, who shared expertise and acquired new knowledge. This allowed extending the scope of the individual assignments, for example incorporating design, simulation and prototyping. To date, more than 20 students from the participating universities have benefited from the mechanisms set in action, with Research Assignments in the fields of Additive Manufacturing, Artificial Intelligence, Life-Cycle Analysis and others. The Metacampus environment has been tested, and the funding sources for the research stays have proved that it can be sustainable in the future through the different Erasmus frameworks.

This Seed Fund collaboration has truly helped to strengthen the collaboration between Aalto, IST, TUDa and UPC universities in research-based teaching in Engineering for Industry. It has served to set up joint courses, to convey better student projects (co-tutorship), to share facilities for teaching, to propose joint PhD topics, and to spark collaborations in research. Also, it has been instrumental in setting up a path to sustainability of the joint research-based teaching, as well as to promote attractive thesis topics to new potential candidates.

The Grenoble Contribution to the Unite! Seed Fund Proposal "Space & Tech UNITE!": Quality Assurance and Product Assurance

M. Bouzat, A. Rauda, E. Kerstel., Jean-Michel Niot, F. De Angelis

This presentation details an innovative educational transformation project undertaken by the University of Grenoble as part of the Unite! Seed Fund initiative, specifically within the "Space & Tech UNITE!" program. The project focuses on Quality Assurance and Product Assurance in the space technology sector.

The core objective was to develop a comprehensive lecture series that could be shared among Unite! partner institutions and potentially extended to a broader audience. The topic of Quality Assurance and Product Assurance in the Space Technology Sector was selected for this pilot project, which fulfilled two key requirements: Lecturer availability and enthusiasm, and an attractive and broadly useful topic that is not commonly offered. The project was made possible with the support of a competent audio-visual team to ensure professional delivery.

The transformation represents a significant pedagogical shift from traditional teaching methods to modern blended-learning approaches. The original format consisted of a conventional 3-hour in-person lecture delivered in French using PowerPoint slides. This traditional approach was completely redesigned into a multi-faceted learning experience delivered in English to maximise accessibility and reach.

Towards a Blueprint for Democratic and Transnational Engineering Education: Insights from the Unite! Learning Network

J. Magrinho, P. Schumann, R. Jerez-Mesa, J. A. Travieso-Rodriguez, P. Groche, B Silva

The development of democratic competencies in higher education increasingly relies on pedagogical models that transcend institutional, linguistic, and disciplinary boundaries. Within this context, the Unite! Learning Network – Breaking Barriers for International Teaching Alliances, funded by the Unite! Seed Fund for Teaching, in its 2025 call, constitutes an experimental framework designed to investigate how digitally mediated, transnational collaboration can enhance student agency, intercultural competence, and ethical awareness in engineering education.

The project responds to persistent challenges in internationalised teaching, such as curricular misalignment, uneven digital maturity, and limited opportunities for sustained intercultural engagement, by establishing a structured learning network across multiple Unite! universities. The model integrates synchronous and asynchronous online collaboration with strategically designed on-site meetings. Students engage in sub-projects embedded within their home

curricula while sharing common milestones, deliverables, and reflective activities with international peers. This multi-layered design enables the systematic study of how distributed teamwork and intercultural dialogue contribute to democratic behaviours such as deliberation, shared decision-making, and negotiation of meaning.

Methodologically, the project adopts a design-based research orientation, enabling teaching teams to test and refine cooperative didactic approaches across institutional contexts iteratively. The intervention includes co-creation of learning tasks, harmonisation of assessment strategies, and joint facilitation of transnational student groups. These practices are analysed with respect to their capacity to build inclusive learning environments, reduce participation asymmetries, and support equitable contributions. These are factors identified as central to democratic cultures in higher education.

Preliminary observations from the initial implementation phase indicate that the digitally supported model enhances students' perception of belonging to a broader European academic community and increases their willingness to engage with diverse perspectives. Early feedback highlights the role of structured intercultural scaffolding in fostering reflective dialogue and ethical awareness, as well as the importance of consistent facilitator coordination to prevent dominance in group interactions.

For academic staff, the project provides empirical insights into the affordances and constraints of international co-teaching, including the negotiation of pedagogical norms, the distribution of workload, and the cultivation of trust across institutional teams. These findings contribute to the broader objective of producing a transferable blueprint for international teaching within the Unite! alliance, one that supports long-term, democratically oriented cooperation and is adaptable to varying disciplinary and institutional contexts.

Overall, the project demonstrates how intentionally designed, digitally enhanced international learning networks can serve as laboratories for democratic engagement, fostering the competencies engineers need to contribute responsibly to increasingly complex and interconnected societies.

Session 2 – track 1

Moderator: Dominik Ruffeis

The Role of Japanese Language Education in Cultivating Leadership Skills among Engineering Students Beyond Europe

A Shirabe

A global perspective has become an essential competency for engineering students. Within the

European higher education context, engineering education is increasingly expected to provide students with opportunities to learn and practice intercultural communication alongside their technical expertise. Non-engineering settings, such as language courses, fall outside students' specialised fields, raising the question of how lecturers can effectively cultivate innovative and appropriate leadership skills in students with limited prior social experience while building a foundation in intercultural communication.

Many labour market conflicts stem from interpersonal relationships, cultural friction, and communication differences that cannot be resolved by specialised knowledge alone. If academia prepares students for these challenges, unnecessary conflicts may be reduced. As a practical example, this presentation examines the Japanese language course offered by the Department of Language and Communication at KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Sweden. International exchange serves as a key form of collaborative activity, connecting KTH's European perspective with the University of Tokyo's Asian perspective. Drawing on insights from the University of Tokyo's exchange program coordinators, the presentation introduces both online and in-person exchange formats and presents concrete proposals for such initiatives. It also considers the role of academia in fostering young engineers' communication skills so they can contribute to the labour market at an early stage.

What can be achieved between Europe and Japan may be even more easily accomplished within Europe itself. From the perspective of internationalisation aimed at fostering appropriate leadership in multilingual and multicultural societies, this presentation considers what "global" means beyond Europe and how active pedagogy can be integrated into everyday teaching to bring higher education institutions closer to the labour market.

Confluences: Uniting disciplines for sustainable solutions

A. Pears, C. Mady, E. Comino, S. Dos Santos Barreiros Proença, A. Clua, P. Pinho, A. Botero, M. P. Ciccariello

The QUORUM seed-finding project in the EU ERASMUS Unite! The consortium explores how disciplinary boundaries can be understood and negotiated in a common context. The project proposes new co-creation pedagogies that link disciplinary understandings with the facilitation and negotiation of vocabulary and the understanding of the complexity of problem-solving in inter- and multidisciplinary contexts.

The project brings together researchers and students from Architecture, Pedagogy, Design, and Urban environments from several Unite partners. The project has workshoped a curriculum co-design activity and subsequently developed a Blended Intensive Program

offering for Unite partner university students. In this final deliverable, the project enhances education by providing new mechanisms for interdisciplinary negotiation of understanding. The skills emphasised in the course are those required to adapt specific disciplinary knowledge to merge with other disciplines in the face of a global challenge.

This presentation will address the pedagogy, philosophical and pedagogical underpinning, and design of the Blended intensive programme offering, as well as participants' perspectives on the value of and challenges with the approach.

Session 2 – track 2

Moderator: Anna Wozna

Shaping the Post-Doc of Tomorrow: Co-Designing Training Pathways for Researcher Mobility

G. Macher, O. Veledar

As the gap between academic research and industrial application narrows, early-stage researchers need a new, hybrid skill set that transcends traditional disciplinary boundaries. The EU-funded INSIGHT project is currently establishing a pilot talent ecosystem to address this need (WP4), specifically focusing on transport and manufacturing.

In this interactive workshop, we invite educators, program managers, and researchers from the Unite! community to help co-design the ideal training framework for the next generation of researchers. We are not presenting a finished curriculum; rather, we are opening our "design floor" to the community. Participants will engage in a structured brainstorming session to answer three critical questions regarding Researcher Training (T4.1) and Career Support (T4.2):

1. Beyond the Technical: Which "soft" competencies (e.g., human-centred design, technology acceptance) are most critical for researchers moving into industry, and how do we best teach them virtually?
2. The Mentorship Challenge: How can universities build effective mentorship programs that bridge the academic-industrial divide without overburdening mentors?
3. Blended Engagement: What are the most effective formats for delivering "Entrepreneurship and IP" training to busy researchers?

Outcome: The insights gathered from this session will directly inform the INSIGHT project's curriculum development. Participants will leave with a shared understanding of common challenges and a network of peers focused on researcher development.

Session 3 – track 1

Moderator: Isabel Ferreirim

Proposal: Higher Education for Democracy through Inner Development Goals: An Experiential and Inter-University Approach

M-H. Bühr

Higher education for democracy requires more than the transmission of knowledge. In a shifting global landscape marked by ecological crises, social fragmentation, and democratic fatigue, universities are increasingly called upon to educate students who critically engage constructively with uncertainty and act responsibly for the common good. Our initiative responds to this challenge by combining international cooperation, experiential learning, and the Inner Development Goals (IDGs) framework.

This presentation introduces a collaborative project that has already been successfully piloted in a beta version at Grenoble INP, providing a solid foundation for collaboration and joint development with other partner universities. We are now considering collaboration with the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya and Technische Universität Darmstadt to develop further the initiative, which builds on a tested pedagogical module entitled Inspire, Imagine, Impact, which integrates “The Week”, an experiential learning programme created by Frédéric and Hélène Laloux and inspired by Otto Scharmer’s Theory U. The aim is to foster democratic capacities, sustainability-oriented mindsets, and international collaboration in higher education.

“The Week” is a structured, one-week collective experience combining high-quality documentary content, facilitated group dialogue, emotional reflection, and concrete action planning. Students are guided to understand the systemic roots of ecological and societal crises, to acknowledge the emotional responses these challenges provoke, and to move from awareness to shared responsibility and action. This approach complements academic teaching by activating lived experience, collective intelligence, and dialogue across differences—key foundations of democratic education.

To deepen and structure this experience, we align the programme with the Inner Development Goals framework, which offers a shared international language for competencies such as self-awareness, critical and systems thinking, empathy, collaboration, courage, and hope. These competencies are essential for democratic participation and sustainable development yet are often underrepresented or weakly assessed in traditional curricula.

The project proposes an inter-university pilot involving bachelor’s or master’s students from at least three European universities. Using a common facilitation protocol and shared assessment tools, students would

participate in joint learning sessions while their development is observed, for example, through reflective journals, pre- and post-self-assessments, peer feedback, and qualitative facilitator observations. The focus of assessment is not on opinion or performance but on reflective capacity, openness to dialogue, and engagement with complexity—making the approach compatible with ECTS frameworks. In parallel, the project is connected to the PRET Observation research initiative, which studies students’ perceptions and representations of transition. This observatory assesses students’ initial levels of awareness, the impact of different pedagogical approaches, and the influence of these approaches on students’ willingness to act and engage. Together, these elements position the project as a scalable “living lab” for democratic and sustainability education within European universities. Internationalisation, education for democracy, and sustainable development through experiential and reflective learning, this initiative contributes concrete, transferable insights into how higher education can empower students to become thoughtful, resilient, and responsible democratic actors in an uncertain world.

Session 3 – track 2

Moderator: Anna Gogolewska

The midwifery role in education: the rebirth of democracy. On teaching ethics and global ethics at universities

A. Hensoldt

The starting point for my presentation is the thought of two American intellectuals whose contributions laid the foundations for discussions of democracy, education, and their complex relation: Jane Addams (1860-1935) and John Dewey (1859-1952). Their works are constantly referenced: the more often, the more democracy in the United States weakens, the more academic freedom and freedom of scientific inquiry are threatened, and the more immigrant rights are threatened.

Jane Addams and John Dewey were collaborators for many years, learning from and discussing social, educational, and democratic ideas.

In 1902, Addams published *Democracy and Social Ethics* where she introduced - in the times of the birth of a new social order - the concept of “social ethics” and “the newer conception of Democracy”: redefining it from a narrow political, voting-based system into an essential “rule of living,” participatory, daily practice, social empathy, and collaboration. One of the most important claims of the book was that “diversified human experience and resultant sympathy (...) are the foundation and guarantee of Democracy.” According to Addams, social equality originated and was supported

by educational rights, which were a guarantee of this “diversified human experience.”

A decade later, Dewey built on this in *Democracy and Education* (1916), stating that: “A democracy is more than a form of government; it is primarily a mode of associated living, of conjoint communicated experience. The extension in space of the number of individuals who participate in an interest so that each has to refer his own action to that of others, and to consider the action of others to give point and direction to his own, is equivalent to the breaking down of those barriers of class, race, and national territory which kept men from perceiving the full import of their activity.” As such democracy is a social competence that needs to be built and strengthened, especially in times of intense social change. Dewey even claims that “democracy has to be born anew every generation, and education is its midwife.”

Democratic competence is supported not only by knowledge of the functioning of democratic institutions, but also by an awareness of social diversity, social inter-dependencies, shared and diverse interests, and the impact of our decisions on the lives of others (sometimes geographically and/or culturally distant). Hence, the significant role of courses in applied ethics and global ethics in shaping such sensitivity, fostering the “diversified human experience” we need more than ever today, not only on a societal but also on a global scale, and finally, in supporting democracy.

This is not psychological or sociological research. I have not operationalised the concepts of democracy, pro-democracy activities, or democratic “inclinations” into any indicators or measures. Therefore, it is not a study in the sense of the social sciences when the results of the test and control groups are compared. Instead, I apply methods characteristic of the humanities: hermeneutic and pragmatic.

My “research groups” were my class students, whom I taught *Global Ethics* from 2021-2025. They were groups composed of people coming from various countries of the world (such as: Nigeria, South Africa, Lebanon, India, Bangladesh, Spain, Italy, Türkiye, Finland, Ukraine, Poland, Kazakhstan, Syria) with various understanding of what democracy is, various experiences of common social life, and with different perceptions of one’s own country’s position on the global political scene.

Discussion on the practical meaning of concrete ethical concepts (for instance: social justice, environmental justice, trans-generational justice) and on ethical thought experiments (such as Hardin’s lifeboat ethics) were inspiration for students to re-think and re-define in discussions concepts of: person, “we”, community, responsibility; they reflect on the structure of decision-making processes and what agency is. All these processes form a hermeneutic circle.

Building on Dewey’s “definition of democracy” reading that “it is primarily a mode of associated living, of conjoint communicated experience” and “each [individual] has to refer his own action to that of others, and to consider the action of others to give point and direction to his own”, I witnessed gradually deepening understanding of what a democratically functioning community is. Moral education can be a means to examine our ill-considered beliefs, learn to understand others, and work together through civic action.

How to teach European Citizenship, Example of ESA

C. Chevallier-Govers

Teaching European citizenship is often based on theoretical courses about the European Union, its institutions, and its policies. While this knowledge is essential, it rarely allows students to experience how European debates and policymaking actually work. The European Student Assembly (ESA), developed within the Erasmus+ project *EUC Voices*, offers a different approach by placing students directly in a participatory and policy-oriented environment.

The European Student Assembly brings together students from universities that are part of the European Universities alliances (57 represented for ESA26). Every year, several thousand students apply to participate in the programme, and around two hundred are selected to take part in the Assembly. Participants come from different countries (33 for ESA26), disciplines, and academic levels, creating a highly diverse group of students. ESA takes place at the European Parliament in Strasbourg, where students present and vote on policy recommendations developed during the preparation phase (from January to April).

The core of the ESA experience is the work carried out in thematic panels. Each panel focuses on a specific European policy challenge and brings together around thirty students. For example, recent panels have addressed topics such as strengthening democracy and citizen participation, scaling the circular economy, improving inclusive public transport systems in Europe, developing digital literacy and cybersecurity, supporting interdisciplinary education, addressing demographic change, and strengthening Europe’s strategic autonomy. Through these panels, students engage directly with some of the most pressing debates currently facing the European Union.

Before meeting in Strasbourg, participants take part in a preparatory phase, which includes online training and collaborative work. During this stage, students learn about the functioning of EU institutions, the process of policymaking, and how to draft policy recommendations. They also begin working with the other members of their panel to define the main issues related to their topic. This preparation allows them to

arrive at the Assembly with a clear understanding of the policy challenges they will discuss.

The work within the panels is highly collaborative. Students analyse their topic, share perspectives from their national and disciplinary contexts, and debate possible policy solutions. With the support of alumni advisors and experts, they draft a series of policy recommendations that aim to address the challenges identified by the panel. These recommendations are then presented and debated during ESA.

One of the most significant moments of the experience for participants is the opportunity to present and vote on their proposals inside the European Parliament in Strasbourg. For many students, this moment represents their first direct engagement with a European political institution and gives a concrete dimension to the discussions that took place during the preparation phase. It also reinforces the idea that their voices and perspectives can contribute to broader European debates.

The impact of the European Student Assembly continues beyond the event itself. After ESA students are encouraged to disseminate the results of their panels within their universities, alliances, and local networks. For example, recommendations produced during ESA have been presented at events organised in universities, shared with European organisations in Brussels, or discussed within European university alliances. Through these activities, the work developed during the panels reaches audiences beyond the Assembly itself.

In this sense, the European Student Assembly can be understood as a practical way of learning European citizenship. By working together across borders, analysing European policy challenges, and presenting their proposals in a real institutional setting, students move beyond theoretical knowledge and experience how democratic debate at the European level can take place. ESA therefore represents not only a platform for student participation but also a concrete pedagogical approach to understanding and practicing European citizenship.

Session 4– track 1

Moderator: Verena Schwägerl-Melchior

EDIFICITECA, a canonical collection of urban buildings to educate future architects.

J. L. Zamora Mestre

Architecture exists in a perpetual state of transition because it constantly materialises the social agreements that enable coexistence and well-being, providing safety and comfort. This materialisation always contributes to culture, modifies the environment, generates technology and fosters

knowledge. In the 20th century, architects became professionals immersed in a consumer society, heavily regulated by legislation that imposes a set of demands, requirements, and contingencies on every architectural problem posed.

Educating these professionals requires informing them (knowledge), training them (enabling them) and making them competent (responsible). Currently, the education of future architects is a task carried out mainly in formal settings (books, the classroom, lectures, school, etc.) and in more informal ones (trips, internships, site visits, exhibitions, etc.). Visiting existing, in-use buildings also has an educational effect on future architects, as it brings together the knowledge acquired in the various disciplinary areas in which teaching is delivered and the integrated understanding derived from reality itself. An architect needs a valued set of lived, interwoven references that enable them, in any given situation, to swiftly identify where the conflict to be resolved lies, where the opportunity to seize lies, what resources they have at their disposal and what room for manoeuvre they possess.

The capacity of the gaze towards architecture has historically been limited by access (books, travel), making it very local and intimate (Zandi-Sayek, 2014). Now we can 'look' much further afield geographically, thanks to telecommunications, and at the same time more selectively, using electronic measuring devices. Can we visit it all? What do we choose? The canons have compiled a census of those works that must be taken into account in study for their educational value, not to be imitated but for their capacity to make evident the possibilities of successful integration among all the aspects that make a work recognised (Baljon, C.J., 2002).

To what extent should our architecture students build their imagination around distant, exceptional, partially documented and little-experienced buildings? The city we live in presents itself to us as one vast, open reference book in which to chart all kinds of educational itineraries and visit canonical buildings. The very endurance of a building in our city over time indicates that its value endures, is evident and recognised as classical. Those buildings that have collapsed have probably already become obsolete and dispensable, although their records may remain in books or museums.

It is proposed that the city be viewed as a landscape in which the buildings selected for the canon can be consulted, read and contemplated as a successful balance of knowledge, circumstances, opportunities and integrated contributions. Each selected building should be a manifest example of a balanced response to a multifaceted question. The built city would thus become an analogue record of integrated knowledge, an opportunity to overcome the limitations of the current visual approach to architecture.

Why teach online?: Three practical reasons from an international education perspective

G. Garcia Siguenza, A. Rauda Gomez

Many higher education teachers remain hesitant about online teaching, particularly regarding workload, assessment, and managing large or diverse student groups. Since Metacampus appeared in 2020, few online resources and courses have been shared on the platform. However, it offers concrete and practical advantages, allowing institutions to reach wider audiences, organise learning efficiently, and maintain high-quality instruction across institutions. To encourage teachers and staff to collaborate actively within Unite. We as instructional designers for digital learning want to share three practical reasons to teach online, illustrated with examples from Metacampus-based programmes and courses. This presentation aims to encourage teaching and pedagogical staff interested in developing or participating in Unite! pedagogical offers to exploit Metacampus as a learning platform.

Landing and Lifting: A Pedagogical Method for Utopian Urban Futures

M. Kemppainen

In times of ecological and social crisis, the present often feels like a cage, trapping us in reactive, short-term thinking. This paper proposes “Landing and Lifting” as a pedagogical method for urban planning, designed to break this paralysis by combining utopian imagination with backcasting: starting from a desired future, then working backwards to identify the conditions and actions needed to reach it.

Grounded in Henri Lefebvre’s right to the city and Bruno Latour’s call to land on Earth, the method redefines utopia not as escapism but as a radical, inclusive practice of co-creating desirable futures in which social justice, ecological resilience, and multispecies well-being are inseparable. Drawing on Donna Haraway’s staying with the trouble, it invites participants to first land – to face the present with honesty – before lifting into collective visions of justice, care, and resilience.

The method unfolds in three phases: first, landing: mapping current urban realities through critical lenses (inequality, power, anthropocentrism); second, lifting: envisioning utopian futures through participatory, backcasting-based exercises centred on questions like “What is well-being? What makes us happy?” and third, bridging: identifying strategic, actionable steps from the present to the desired future.

Designed for planners, educators, researchers, and activists, Landing and Lifting cultivates planetary citizenship – the capacity to imagine and act toward futures that transcend anthropocentrism and short-termism. It responds to the urgent need to re-enchanted

urban futures through grounded, collective, and politically aware dreaming. This paper outlines the theoretical foundations, methodological design, and anticipated pedagogical outcomes, inviting collaboration and experimentation in future iterations.

Session 4 – track 2

Moderator: Ernest Ampadu

Value-driven education? Democratic competence and the educational role of Unite!

Björn Kjellgren and Marta Serrano Van Der Laan (Multilingual and Multicultural Training Centre (M&M))

How might Unite! make the value dimension of its educational mission more explicit? While the alliance has articulated clear ambitions in education, research, and collaboration, the role of values within these efforts is often less visible than that of knowledge and skills – frequently residing in the hidden curriculum, i.e., in implicit norms and expectations rather than explicitly articulated educational aims.

Unite!’s policy on multilingualism and multiculturalism provides a point of departure. It frames linguistic and cultural diversity as resources for fostering global competence and calls for their systematic integration across academic activities. Taken seriously, this position raises a further question: to what extent should the values underpinning global competence be more deliberately articulated within the alliance’s shared educational space?

As alliances deepen integration through shared academic initiatives, greater visibility of their normative foundations may support coherence across institutional and national contexts. Participants are invited to consider whether the Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC) developed by the Council of Europe could assist such reflection. By conceptualising competence as the behavioural expression of values, attitudes, skills, and critical understanding, the framework offers a vocabulary for addressing dimensions of education that often remain implicit in university settings.

The question is timely. European universities operate in societies marked by political tension and competing interpretations of democratic principles. Engaging more explicitly with democratic competence may therefore clarify the alliance’s moral orientation while creating space to examine differing understandings of European values rather than presuming consensus.

This roundtable, a structured discussion, invites participants to explore whether the RFCDC could serve as a shared reference for articulating and fostering the value dimension of Unite!’s educational mission, and to consider both its connections to existing practices and the practical limits of alliance-level alignment.